

$\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ frequency^{9,10}. The presence of broad and weak non-ligand band at 310–370 cm^{-1} in the Zn^{II} complexes may be due to $\nu_{\text{Zn-N}}$ mode^{11,12}.

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Study of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II) and Cobalt(II) with Nitrilotriacetic Acid and Salicylidene-2-iminopyridine

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IN this communication, we report the results of our potentiometric investigation on the equilibrium study of ternary complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} with nitrilotriacetic acid (NTA) as the primary ligand (A) and the Schiff base, salicylidene-2-iminopyridine (SAP or HL), as the secondary ligand in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium (ionic strength, $I=0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$) and at 30 and 40°.

Experimental

A.R. grade or purified chemicals were used in the study. A 0.02 M solution of salicylidene-2-iminopyridine was made in lime-distilled ethanol. Solutions of the metal nitrates (0.01 M) were made in 0.1 M HNO_3 . Nitrilotriacetic acid (0.01 M) was used as the trisodium salt. A ECL 5651 digital pH-meter with a combined glass electrode assembly was used. Representative pH-titration curves are shown in Fig. 1.

Practical proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were calculated by Bjerrums method^{3,5} as

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves at 30° in 50% (v/v) ethanol-water medium ($I=0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$): (a) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M SAP + 0.1M KNO_3 , (b) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M NTA + 0.002M metal nitrate + 0.002M SAP + 0.1M KNO_3 , (c) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M metal nitrate + 0.002M SAP + 0.1M KNO_3 , (d) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M NTA + 0.1M KNO_3 , (e) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.002M NTA + 0.002M metal nitrate + 0.1M KNO_3 , and (f) 0.02M HNO_3 + 0.1M KNO_3 , titrant, NaOH (0.9861M), initial volume of each solution = 50 ml.

modified by Irving and Rossotti⁴ and others⁵. Duplicate titrations using varying ligand concentrations were performed to ensure the absence of ligand hydrolysis under the experimental condition.

Results and Discussion

In the mixed ligand system it is observed that metal-NTA curve (e) (Fig. 1) departs NTA curve (d) at low pH showing that metal-NTA complex formation takes place at low pH. Metal-NTA complex species occurring at $\text{pH} \approx 4$ is stable even at higher pH values. The mixed ligand titration curve (b) diverges from the secondary ligand titration curve (a) after complete formation of (metal-NTA) complex. It may, therefore, be assumed that the secondary ligand (SAP) would combine with metal-NTA complex species to form the ternary species.

It is evident from Table 1 that lower value of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$ than $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$ and $\log K_{\text{ML}_2}^{\text{ML}}$ is attributed to the greater repulsion between NTA^{3-} anion and L^- anion as compared to that between two L^- anions. Such repulsion is however absent in the formation of ML species. Stability of $\text{M}(\text{NTA})(\text{L})$ complexes

is found to be the same order, $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Co}^{\text{II}} \sim \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$ as for the corresponding binary ML complexes.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES IN 50% (v/v) ETHANOL-WATER MEDIUM

$I=0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$

Cation	$\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$	$\log K_{\text{ML}_2}^{\text{ML}}$	$\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{MA}}$		$\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}$
	30°	30°	30°	40°	
H ⁺	9.13	6.58	—	—	—
Cu ^{II}	6.65	4.60	3.20	3.17	-3.45
Ni ^{II}	4.70	3.98	2.58	2.47	-2.17
Co ^{II}	4.53	3.48	2.73	2.73	-1.75

The $\Delta \log K_{\text{M}}$ values^a (Table 1) for all M(NTA)-(L) complexes are negative. Higher negative value of $\Delta \log K_{\text{Cu}}$ as compared to $\Delta \log K_{\text{Ni}}$ probably arises out of Jahn-Teller distortion in the case of Cu^{II} complexes.

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Phenyl Acetate Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Zinc(II) with Nitrogen Donor Ligands

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In this communication, we report the studies on Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} , phenyl acetates with quinoline, isoquinoline and 3-methylpyridine.

Experimental

Metal carbonates were reacted in stoichiometric proportion with alcoholic solution of phenylacetic acid on a water-bath. Alcoholic solution of metal phenyl acetates were treated with nitrogen ligands in 1:2 proportion and the solution refluxed for 0.5 h over a water-bath. Volume of the solution

was reduced to 5 ml by rotary vacuum evaporator and kept overnight when crystalline compounds separated out. The compounds were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum. All complexes were found to be crystalline—Ni and Cu complexes green, Co complexes pink and Zn complexes white. Metal and nitrogen in the complexes were estimated by standard methods; conductance in acetone, magnetic moment at room temperature (Table 1), ir spectra (KBr) and electronic spectra (chloroform) were recorded.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF PHENYL ACETATE COMPLEXES

Compd ^a	Conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)	
			Metal	N
NiL_2Q_2	8.5	2.9	9.95 (10.07)	4.45 (4.77)
$\text{NiL}_2(\text{I.Q})_2$	9.2	2.98	9.83 (10.07)	4.52 (4.77)
$\text{NiL}_2(\beta\text{-pio})_2$	8.1	3.15	11.14 (11.40)	5.28 (5.44)
CoL_2Q_2	9.5	4.84	9.86 (10.03)	4.53 (4.77)
$\text{CoL}_2(\text{I.Q})_2$	8.8	4.96	9.91 (10.03)	4.55 (4.77)
$\text{CoL}_2(\beta\text{-pio})_2$	10.2	5.1	11.22 (11.46)	5.26 (5.44)
CuL_2Q_2	11.5	1.75	10.56 (10.74)	4.48 (4.73)
$\text{CuL}_2(\text{I.Q})_2$	11.8	1.83	11.62 (10.74)	4.48 (4.73)
$\text{CuL}_2(\beta\text{-pio})_2$	12.6	1.88	12.01 (12.28)	5.26 (5.39)
ZnL_2Q_2	10.5	—	10.92 (11.02)	4.51 (4.72)
$\text{ZnL}_2(\text{I.Q})_2$	13.8	—	10.86 (11.02)	4.60 (4.72)
$\text{ZnL}_2(\beta\text{-pio})_2$	14.7	—	12.25 (12.54)	5.22 (5.37)

^aQ=Quinoline, I.Q=Isoquinoline, β -pio=3-methylpyridine.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes are crystalline and have the composition ML_2B_2 , where L is the phenyl acetate and B is the nitrogen base. These are fairly low melting solids and soluble in common organic solvents. Lower values of molar conductance suggest their non-electrolytic nature. Magnetic moment values of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes at room temperature (25°) are indicative of high-spin octahedral configuration. Cu^{II} complexes have magnetic moment in the normal range.

In sodium phenyl acetate asymmetric and symmetric C=O stretching frequencies appear at 1610 and 1400 cm^{-1} , respectively¹. These bands are shifted to slightly lower frequency regions in the transition metal phenyl acetates and shift to higher frequency regions (around 1420 and 1630 cm^{-1}) respectively, in the complexes with nitrogen ligands. Further, most of the bands due to free nitrogen ligands are shifted to lower frequency region in most of the complexes indicating their coordination to the metal ions. This has been further supported